

Obstacles to the Application of Knowledge Management from the Point of View of the Employees at the Technical University of Palestine (Kadoorei)

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Abstract: *The aim of this study is to identify the determinants and obstacles to the application of knowledge management at the Technical University of Palestine (Kadoorei). The study population consists of all 310 employees of the Technical University of Palestine (Kadoorei). In order to achieve this, the researchers used a questionnaire consisting of (25) paragraphs dealing with the determinants and obstacles of the application of knowledge management at the Technical University of Palestine (Kadoorei) distributed to 74 employees. After the process of distribution of the questionnaire collected and coded and entered into the computer processed statistically using the Statistical Program of Social Sciences (SPSS).*

The results of the study indicate the percentage of approval of the constraints of the application of knowledge management at the Technical University of Palestine (Kadoorei) between the low and the large, and the relative weight of the whole axis (68.2). The following paragraphs were obtained: (Obstacles to the complex administrative procedures pursued by the University, and the scarcity of training courses in this field, Over-centralization, the lack of an independent organizational unit to oversee knowledge management, resistance to change, low level of participation of staff in the decision-making process, and the incentive system pursued by the university, and to try to ignore the ideas of the workers and the scarcity of individuals specialized in knowledge management) a high approval rate and this indicates the existence of imbalance in administrative procedures and weakness in the development of human cadres and attention to it. There were no statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) in the mean responses of the sample of the study towards the obstacles to the application of knowledge management at the Technical University of Palestine (Kadoorei) due to variables (gender, nature of work, Education Level, years of service). There were statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) in the responses of the sample of the study towards the constraints of the application of knowledge management at the Technical University of Palestine (Kadoorei) due to the variable of specialization and for the level of specialization (human sciences) in terms of the arithmetic average which reached (3.63) while the average level of (applied sciences) was (3.23).

In light of the results of the previous study, the researchers recommended a number of recommendations, namely, the need to pay attention to the principle of knowledge management in order to raise the university's reputation and academic reputation at home and abroad, improve its services to students and the local community and knowledge management is one of the most prominent features of modern management in academic institutions. And work to accept change and shift towards knowledge management by encouraging the recruitment and recruiting human cadres specialized in this area and the training of existing cadres. And the need for the university to systematically monitor the knowledge and information in the academic field from available sources because of its importance in the academic process and in the development of university work.

Keywords: Knowledge Management, Palestine Technical University (Kadoorei), Palestine.

1. INTRODUCTION

The institutions' awareness of the importance of survival and continuity in an environment of complexity and constant change in all its fields (economic, political, social, technological, etc.) has to constantly strive to provide high standards in the performance of its work and activities in a way that enables it to Knowledge management is one of the ways in which organizations can manage, disseminate, develop and maintain the knowledge base of the human element, which is the most important source of enterprise resources and the most capable of upgrading them and transferring them to the institutions. Universality.

Knowledge management also plays an important role in the development of institutions, especially universities, because of its intellectual and knowledge assets. Therefore, it has become more capable of keeping pace with development and achieving excellence in the knowledge society.

Modern institutions, including institutions of higher education, face Large and unprecedented challenges due to the changes resulting from the information and technological revolution, in addition to the fierce competition between different institutions and the challenges that have emerged in the various sectors, especially the educational ones, so it was necessary to face this competition and challenges in order to

keep pace The wheel of change and facing the competition imposed by the advanced reality on the basis of science and knowledge (Al-Othman, 2013).

In order to face these challenges and to deal with them, it was necessary to introduce knowledge to represent the most important strategic source in institution building, and to meet the challenges posed by the conditions of the advanced age, but became the most powerful and influential factor in the success or failure of knowledge. Is an essential component of the organization's production, as well as its capital and work, while others view the need to deal with the knowledge that the organization possesses as a capital asset that can have material value within the assets and assets of that organization (Abu Khudair, 2009).

In light of the above, the present study aims to identify the obstacles that may limit the possibility of applying knowledge management, especially in technical universities, as they are the most complex and changing.

2. PROBLEM STATEMENT

The role of the university has evolved beyond its attempt to acquire and transfer knowledge from generation to generation to the need to work on its production, dissemination, development and preservation. (Barakat and Hassan, 2009) (Khoj, 2008) International reality and global transformations, the most important of which are the development of modern educational systems such as distance learning, the development of scientific research, the increasing use of electronic media at the university, increased scientific cooperation among higher education institutions, and the internationalization of education. And the difficulty of balancing the quantity and quality of the work system in these institutions, the difficulty of adapting to the market requirements in these communities, and the weak outputs of the institutions represented in the huge number of Graduates who are not suitable for modern developments in light of changing the nature and forms of careers of the future to address these challenges, many studies have recommended the interest of universities in the training related to knowledge and increase experience in the generation of knowledge and increase cooperation between universities. Therefore, this study came to answer the question of the President, which is:

What obstacles can limit the application of knowledge management at the Technical University of Palestine (Kadoorei) from the point of view of its employees?

The following sub-questions are obtained from the main question:

Q1-: What are the main obstacles to the application of knowledge management at the Technical University of Palestine (Kadoorei)?

Q2-: Is the level of employee awareness of the obstacles facing the application of knowledge management at the Technical University of Palestine (Kadoorei) different in regard to (gender, Work Nature, Education Level, Specialization, years of experience)?

3. RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

The study examined the following main hypothesis: There were no statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the mean responses of the sample of the study towards the constraints of the application of knowledge management at the Technical University of Palestine (Kadoorei) Academic, Academic, Years of Experience).

The following zero hypotheses emerged:

1. There were no statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the mean responses of the sample of the study towards the constraints of the application of knowledge management at the Technical University of Palestine (Kadoorei) due to gender variable.
2. There are no statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the averages of the study sample responses towards obstacles to the application of knowledge management in the Palestine Technical University (Kadoorei) due to the variable Work Nature.
3. There are no statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the averages of the study sample responses towards obstacles to the application of knowledge management in the Palestine Technical University (Kadoorei) attributed the Education Level variable.
4. There are no statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the averages of the study sample responses towards obstacles to the application of knowledge management in the Palestine Technical University (Kadoorei) due to the variable of Specialization.
5. There are no statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the averages of the study sample responses towards obstacles to the application of knowledge management in the Palestine Technical University (Kadoorei) due to the variable years of experience.

4. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

This study aims to achieve the following objectives:

1. Knowledge of the theoretical concepts of knowledge management and its dimensions and the most important requirements for application.
2. Statement of the most important obstacles to the application of knowledge management at the Technical University of Palestine (Kadoorei).
3. Identify the extent to which employees are aware of the obstacles facing the application of knowledge management at the Technical University of Palestine (Kadoorei) by gender, Work Nature, Education Level, Specialization, years of experience.
4. Making recommendations may contribute to the development of knowledge management in technical

universities and overcome constraints that may limit them.

5. RESEARCH IMPORTANCE

The importance of the study is that it presents a very important topic, namely the disclosure of the obstacles to the application of knowledge management in a Palestinian university as an institution responsible for higher education in the northern Palestinian governorates. The previous studies on the subject of knowledge management focused on the interest in their application and rarely concerned with the obstacles, determinants, and controls which limit their application; thus, the importance of this study is to contribute to the following:

1. Knowledge of the current status of knowledge management at the Technical University of Palestine (Kadoorei) in order to develop future visions in this field.
2. Knowledge of the obstacles and limitations that impede the application of knowledge management in the university mentioned.
3. Assisting the authorities responsible for planning higher education in Palestine to avoid the deficiencies in the application of knowledge management in the Palestinian universities.
4. The scientific enrichment of research in the field of knowledge management and obstacles to its achievement in the technical education sector.

6. RESEARCH LIMITS AND SCOPE

1. **Human Limit:** This study was limited to surveying the views of a sample of employees at the Technical University of Palestine (Kadoorei) supervisors and administrators.
2. **Institutional limitation:** This study was applied to the Technical University of Palestine (Kadoorei).
3. **Time Limits:** This study was implemented in 2018.

7. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Knowledge Management:

The university is the most important and first institution that must take the principle of knowledge management, it is one of the most appropriate institutions for that. As for the concept of knowledge management in higher education institutions, it is still considered relatively new, but it has received large attention from researchers and researchers in these institutions in pursuit of scientific excellence and research, quality and academic accreditation. Abu Khudair, (2009) defines it as a framework or layer that enables individuals working in an educational institution to develop a set of practices to collect information and share what they know, resulting in behaviors or behaviors that improve the level of services and products provided by the institution.

Knowledge management is one of the latest concepts in management science, which is considered one of the most

vital features of activities that affect the quality and quality of work. The concept occupied a prominent and vital place in various administrative, technical, scientific and educational fields (AL- Sawy, 2007)

Al-Baghdadi and Al-Abbadi (2009) believe that knowledge management is a set of processes aimed at transforming intellectual resources into tangible values by focusing on intangible assets. Nour El Din (2010) considers the engineering and organization of the human environment and processes Which helps the organization to produce and generate knowledge through its selection, organization, use and dissemination, and finally transfer and transfer important information and experiences that the organization has to the right people at the right time to be organized in various administrative activities and employ them in good decision making, problem solving, organizational learning and strategic planning.

El-Meligy (2010) defines it as all the strategic efforts of the university education institution through which it seeks to achieve competitive advantage by collecting and investing its intellectual assets, improving the different practices of the working individuals and optimizing the use of the information in its databases, Quality in performance and increased productivity of the whole university. It is a broadening and deepening of knowledge within an appropriate framework that is learning organizations that support their employees and allow them to express and benefit from this learning for the benefit of the organization (Hislope, 2009).

Bulter (2006) argues that knowledge management is a combination of accumulated experience, values, contextual information, and expert insight that provide a general framework for evaluating and integrating new experiences and information. Arora and Raosaheb (2011) sees the process by which the organization uses its social intelligence to achieve its strategic objectives. A set of processes that seek to change the organization's current pattern of knowledge processing to enhance knowledge both within and at the level of its output (Firestone, McElory, 2005).

The researchers define them as procedural processes resulting from the experiences and concepts adopted by the administrative institution to improve and improve the level of performance and improve them for the better.

Objectives of Knowledge Management:

Higher education institutions, in order to compete and excel in their markets, need to be characterized by their services and knowledge, and to be the leader in their field to ensure the satisfaction of their internal and external customers alike. The implementation of knowledge management in all the tasks, activities and processes carried out at the university, including (teaching, scientific research, community service, strategic planning, administrative services, student services and information resources) (Al Hila et al., 2017), (Al Hila and Al Shobaki, 2017), (Al Shobaki et al., 2017), (Abu Naser et al., 2017).

AL-Sawy (2007) argues that knowledge management within the organization is generally aimed at achieving the following objectives:

1. To streamline processes and reduce costs by eliminating lengthy or unnecessary procedures.
2. To improve customer service by reducing the time it takes to deliver the required services.
3. To adopt the idea of creativity by encouraging the principle of free flow of ideas.
4. To increase financial revenue by marketing products and services more effectively.
5. To activate knowledge and intellectual capital to improve service delivery.

Al-Othman (2013) believes that knowledge management aims to build intellectual capital that serves the interests and objectives of the organization, to generate knowledge and to reveal its resources from different sources and to employ them in decision making, problem solving, organizational learning and strategic planning, through available methods and means.

The researchers believe that one of the most important objectives of knowledge management is the ability to absorb the changes that occur especially as we are talking about a technical university in the sense that the mechanism of change and development is faster than the capabilities and potential of these universities material, moral and human. Where investment in the human element and care and development of one of the pillars of continuity in the light of this change.

Reasons for the emergence of knowledge management:

Al-Saad and Harim (2004) believe that there are a number of reasons for encouraging and managing knowledge:

1. Globalization of the economy where information moves and moves at the speed of light.
2. The ability of modern and advanced technologies to obtain data, information and knowledge.
3. The worker's ability to absorb and analyze these data.
4. Increased competition among organizations, rapid and increased innovations, new discoveries and rapid changes in various areas.

Thus, it is necessary for organizations to recognize that knowledge management and creative processes are the means to remain in a strong competitive position under harsh, difficult and rapidly changing working conditions.

Justifications for university adoption of knowledge management (Al hila et al., 2017):

The researchers (Mikulecka & Mikulecky) identified a set of justifications for this:

- Universities typically have a modern information infrastructure.
- Sharing knowledge with others is normal between faculty members and students in general.

- One of the natural requirements that students seek to reach - by joining the university - is to get knowledge from easily accessible sources as soon as possible.
- Universities generally have a trustworthy regulatory environment, with no member hesitating to disseminate and disseminate knowledge.
- The Large similarity between modern universities and business organizations, in terms of the tendency of universities to offer a number of activities, educational and research services, and consulting for a fee under the framework of the so-called educational Market, so any method, or method may give the University a competitive advantage may be of interest For those universities, knowledge management is one of the most advanced technologies in this direction.

Obstacles to the application of knowledge management:

Al-Suhaimi (2009) sees several factors impeding the application of knowledge management in organizations, and it is important to avoid them that can lead to knowledge management failure:

1. The absolute perception of knowledge as being outside the minds of individuals, while most implicit knowledge lies in their minds.
2. Lack of awareness of the importance and role of implicit knowledge and discouraging its manifestation.
3. Isolation of knowledge about their uses.
4. Replace technological communication rather than direct dialogue.
5. Relying on the knowledge stored in knowledge bases, and not paying attention to the flow of knowledge and new knowledge.
6. Intense centralism and fear of a job by a centralized management approach may not help to transfer and share knowledge among the staff of the organization and the source of such centralization is sometimes a fear of a job.
7. Ignorance of the importance of transferring knowledge not to pay attention to self-development and not to monitor important, virtual and implicit knowledge.
8. Knowledge management is not included in the organization's strategic plans, which reduces its ability to recognize the value of knowledge management and the need to provide a system for it.

Al-Othman (2013) adds other obstacles:

1. Weak use of available techniques.
2. Low level of participation of decision-making staff in FAO.
3. The existence of negative organizational conflicts.
4. Weak documentation of implicit knowledge (experiences, skills and creations) and discouragement to show them.
5. Lack of qualified human resources to perform knowledge management tasks.
6. Lack of support from senior management.

7. Lack of sufficient financial resources to implement knowledge management.

8. LITERATURE REVIEW

- Study of (Shamia et al., 2018) aimed to use the Asian knowledge model “APO” as a determinant for performance excellence in universities and identifying the most effecting factors on it. This study was applied on Al-Azhar University in Gaza strip. The result of the study showed that (APO) model is valid as a measure and there are four dimensions in the model affecting significantly more than the others (university processes, KM leadership, personnel, and KM outputs). Furthermore, performance excellence produced through modernizing the means of education, curriculum development, technology and flexibility in the organizational structure. The study recommends expanding the usage of (APO) model, enhancing the role of knowledge leadership, technology, organizational flexibility, sharing culture and incentive systems that encouraging innovation.
- Study of (Abu Amuna et al., 2017) aimed to identify the role of Knowledge-Based computerized management information systems in the administrative decision-making process and that can lead to a reduction or limitation of potential problems, especially those related to unintended bias and ambiguous, these problems controls the collection of information for the primary knowledge base, and given that the knowledge based systems, computer information systems constitute a dynamic, constructed and programmed throughout specialized knowledge based systems programming languages. That is, they learn from the experience and knowledge gained. They can be used to build intelligent business decision making systems. The research found a set of recommendations, including: the need to use knowledge-based computerized information systems in the administrative decision-making process. And the configuration of tires capable of using modern applications of information technology in various administrative levels. As well as benefit from the advantages offered by the knowledge-based with respect to the effort, time and money and to be able to respond to environmental conditions and changes.
- Study of (Abu Naser et al., 2016) aimed to measure knowledge management maturity in higher education institutions to determine the impact of knowledge management on high performance. Also the study aims to compare knowledge management maturity between universities and intermediate colleges. This study was applied on five higher education institutions in Gaza strip, Palestine. Asian productivity organization model was applied to measure Knowledge Management Maturity. Second dimension which assess high performance was developed by the authors. The controlled sample was (917). Several statistical tools were used for data analysis and hypotheses testing, including reliability correlation using Cronbach’s coefficient alpha, “ANOVA”, Simple Linear Regression and Step Wise Regression. The overall findings of the current study show that maturity level is in the second level. Findings also support the main hypothesis and its sub- hypotheses. The most important factors effecting high performance are: Processes, knowledge management leadership, People, knowledge management Outcomes. Furthermore, the current study is unique by the virtue of its nature, scope and way of implied investigation, as it is the first comparative study between universities and intermediate colleges in Gaza Strip that explores the status of knowledge management maturity using the Asian Productivity Model.
- Study of (Abu Naser et al., 2016) the paper assesses Knowledge Management Maturity (KMM) in the universities to determine the impact of knowledge management on performance excellence. This study was applied on Al-Azhar University and Al-Quds Open University in Gaza strip, Palestine. This paper depends on Asian productivity organization model that used to assess KMM. Second dimension which assess performance excellence was developed by the authors. The controlled sample was (610). Several statistical tools were used for data analysis and hypotheses testing, including reliability Correlation using Cronbach’s coefficient alpha, “ANOVA”, Simple Linear Regression and Step Wise Regression. The overall findings of the current study suggest that KMM is suitable for measuring performance excellence. KMM assessment shows that both universities maturity level is in level three. Findings also support the main hypothesis and it is sub- hypotheses. The most important factors effecting performance excellence are: Processes, KM leadership, People, KM Outcomes. Furthermore the current study is unique by the virtue of its nature, scope and way of implied investigation, as it is the first comparative study in the universities of Palestine explores the status of KMM using the Asian productivity Model.
- Study of (Al-Othman, 2013), which aims to identify the reality of the application of knowledge management at Naif Arab University for Security Sciences, the obstacles it faces and ways to develop its application. The researchers used the descriptive analytical method, and the questionnaire as a tool for study was applied to a sample of faculty member’s amounted to (103) individuals. The results of the study showed a moderate degree of approval among the sample on the reality of the application of knowledge management as well as the existence of a consensus on the existence of significant obstacles that prevent the application of knowledge management in the university, in addition to the absence of statistically significant differences in the study sample trends due to variables: gender, And Work Nature. The study recommended the continuation of the

development of the University's information systems, and the adoption and support of the university administration for the concept of knowledge management and benefiting from the experiences of successful institutions in this field in addition to holding training courses and scientific activities in the field of knowledge management.

- Study of (Al-Zatma, 2011) aimed at identifying the relationship and the type of influence between the requirements of knowledge management and its operations, and distinguished the institutional performance in the middle technical colleges. And the questionnaire as a tool to collect the necessary data from the study community composed of all faculty members and heads of the full-time administrative departments in five faculties (455). The study found that there is a high degree of availability of knowledge needs (data and information, implicit knowledge, explicit knowledge, infrastructure, technology, and human capital) in intermediate technical colleges with a medium degree of knowledge awareness in its forms (planning and implementation, And information security). The study concluded with a number of recommendations, including the need to adopt knowledge management as an input to improve and develop the individual and institutional performance of the intermediate technical colleges, to develop knowledge and develop storage methods, expand the participatory processes through the appropriate environment, and develop individual and institutional performance and adopt an incentive system that rewards knowledge efforts.
- Study of (Madi, 2010), which aims to demonstrate the impact of applying the concept of knowledge management in ensuring the quality of education at the Islamic University of Gaza. A questionnaire was used as a measuring tool applied to a sample of the teaching staff of the university, which numbered (275) members. The study reached a number of results, the most important of which are differences in the opinions of the respondents on the knowledge management infrastructure due to the degree and the years of experience. A number of recommendations were made, including the need to increase the electronic communication between the Islamic University and other universities in the aspects of scientific cooperation in addition to the need to pay attention to e-learning through the computerization of libraries and the provision of appropriate technology to reach them.
- Study of (Al-Shahrani, 2010), aimed at increasing the knowledge of researchers and practitioners on how to employ knowledge management at King Fahd Security College in Saudi Arabia and the obstacles that prevent it. The study used the descriptive descriptive method through a questionnaire which was distributed to a sample of 68 employees. The study found that there are many areas for the application of knowledge management in most departments of the college, with obstacles that can limit the success of knowledge management, the most important of which are the lack of specialized personnel, ignoring the ideas of others, weak documentation of implicit knowledge, lack of work teams, Imposed by the college administration.
- The Study of (Girard and McIntyre, 2010) aimed at clarifying the optimal use of the knowledge management model in the public sector institutions. The researchers adopted the case study methodology to achieve the research objectives through the case study of the federal government in Canada and the knowledge management model in government institutions Canadian. The researchers found that the five components of knowledge management (technology, leadership, culture, processes, and standards) have contributed positively to enabling organizations to achieve their goals. Therefore, the researchers recommended applying this five-dimensional model as a comprehensive model of all knowledge management components.
- The Study of (Kasim, 2010), which aimed at explaining the important role of knowledge management practices in improving the performance and efficiency of public sector institutions, and how to improve the performance of government through the application of knowledge management. The researchers used the analytical descriptive method through the distribution of a questionnaire on a random sample of (500) employees in (28) Ministry. The results showed a positive relationship between knowledge management practices and job efficiency in Malaysian public sector institutions. The study recommended that senior management should understand the factors and elements that contribute to the effectiveness of the job performance as well as the existence of a number of obstacles that limit performance improvement.
- The Study of (Khubash, 2009) aimed at identifying the factors affecting the application of knowledge management within the University of Jordan and the obstacles to its application through the use of descriptive analytical methodology on a sample of (120) members of the university administration. This study has reached several conclusions, the most important of which is that the process of applying knowledge management within the University of Jordan is also medium. It also concluded that the most important obstacles to the good implementation of knowledge management are the lack of acceptance of change and development, weak communication within the university and the presence of patronage and moderation. The results also showed that there is no statistically significant relationship between the various factors related to the study and the application of knowledge management within the University of Jordan and its constraints due to the

variables of gender, age, experience, occupation and scientific qualification.

- The Study of (Singh, 2008), which aimed to investigate the relationship between leadership patterns and knowledge management, and the impact of these patterns on the knowledge management practices in an Indian software company. To achieve the objectives of the study, the researchers used the descriptive and analytical method as a study tool.) Employees working in a software production company in India. The study found that the leadership and support leadership style has a negative impact on knowledge management practices, while the consultative management style and negotiator have a positive impact. The study recommended the application of knowledge management as it gives employees the freedom to think and act.

Commenting on previous studies:

It is clear from the presentation of previous studies the diversity of its purposes and their differences among them. The Arab studies were conducted to identify the obstacles and the reality of the application of knowledge management such as Shamia et al. (2018), Abu Amuna et al., (2017), (Abu Naser et al., 2016), Al-Othman, 2013), (Al-Zatma, 2011), (Madi, 2010), (Al-Shahrani, 2010) and (Khubash, 2009) Such as Girard and McIntyre (2010), Kasim (2010) and Singh (2008).

This study is similar to a study (Al-Othman, 2013), (Al-Zatma, 2011), (Madi, 2010), (Al-Shahrani, 2010), (Khubash, 2009), (Shamia et al., 2108), (Abu Naser et al., 2017), (Abu Naser et al., 2016), which aimed to identify the application of knowledge management in the institutions of higher education and the descriptive approach used. Foreign studies have differed with the current study in terms of goal.

This study differs with previous studies in the period of time and the sector in which it was applied. It was applied to a technical university in the northern governorates. The obstacles were identified from the point of view of the university employees.

Palestine Technical University - (Kadoorei): (PTUK)

It is one of the institutions of higher education in Palestine. It is the first and only governmental university in the West Bank to follow the Ministry of Education and Higher Education. It was established in 1930 as an agricultural school for the benefit of the Palestinian society and then developed under the Palestinian National Authority to become a college that offers diploma programs in many disciplines and then turned into a university college, "Palestine Technical College (Kadoorei)" to provide technical programs at different levels (diploma and bachelor). The college was transferred to a university with the approval and approval of the National Commission for Accreditation, Quality, and the Minister of Education and Higher Education. The development of the organizational structure and the academic, administrative and technical staff was carried out. A development plan was developed in the first two and a half years, during which new colleges were established and special and complementary specialties were opened for the other disciplines available in the other Palestinian universities to meet the needs of the local and Arab And also international (<https://www.ptuk.edu.ps>).

9. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

The researchers followed the analytical descriptive approach to its relevance for the purposes of this study, which is the method that is concerned with the phenomenon as it is in fact, and is working to describe, analyze and relate to other phenomena, where the researchers relied on sources of information related to the subject of study, and analysis, and then data collection by the questionnaire, Which was prepared based on theoretical framework and previous studies.

- 1. Community and Study:** The study population consisted of all (310) employees of the Technical University of Palestine (Kadoorei). The researchers selected a simple random sample of (74) administrative and faculty members. The characteristics of the study sample are as follows:

Table 1: Distribution of the sample of the study by its variables

Variable	Category	Repetition	Percentage %
Gender	Male	42	56.8
	Female	32	43.2
Work Nature	Administrative	46	62.2
	Faculty member	28	37.8
Education Level	Diploma	15	20.3
	BA	29	39.1
	M.A.	17	23.0
	Ph.D.	13	17.6
Specialization	Applied Sciences	41	55.4
	Human sciences	33	44.6
Years of Experience	1-4	32	43.3
	5-9	14	18.9
	10-14	12	16.2

	15 and more	16	21.6
Total		74	100

The following table shows the following:

- The increase in the proportion of males compared to females indicates a preference for the male component in female employment. This indicates that there is a defect in the selection and recruitment procedures or a kind of favoritism because the nature of the society is masculine, especially in administrative and supervisory positions. We see that the tendency is often to choose males from females.
 - The high proportion of administrative staff compared to faculty members due to the permanent presence of members of the administrative body, while there is difficulty in communicating with faculty members to vary the times of lectures.
 - As for the Education Level, we find that the largest percentage was for the bachelor's degree and above. This is due to the interest of the educational institutions and their focus on selection and appointment to the holders of higher qualifications due to the nature of their academic work.
 - As for the specialization, we see that the largest proportion was applied science. This is due to the fact that the nature of the university is technical and the focus is on specializations of practical nature, especially the engineering field.
 - With regard to the years of experience, we find that the largest proportion of those who have years of experience (1-4) and this is the result of the expansion of the University in the specializations offered in addition to the increasing turnout of students to the university during this period.
- 2. Study tool:** The questionnaire was used as a primary tool for gathering information in order to identify constraints that could limit the application of knowledge management. It consists of two main parts: (personal data, constraints on the application of knowledge management), which are as follows:
- The first section is information and personal data about the respondents (gender, nature of work, qualification, specialization, years of service).
 - The second section is the obstacles to the application of knowledge management at the Technical University of Palestine (Kadoorei) and it consists of (25) paragraphs.
- 3. Tool Validation:** In order to ensure the safety of the study questions, the validity of the study was verified by

presenting it to a group of arbitrators with expertise and experience in the field of administrative sciences, and asked them to express their opinion on the paragraphs of the questionnaire by deleting, modifying and proposing new paragraphs and appropriate tool for the subject of the study. The tool of the study became in its final form a component of (25) paragraph.

- 4. Stability of the tool:** In order to extract the stability coefficient of the tool, Cronbach's coefficient alpha equation was used to determine the internal consistency of the resolution paragraphs. It reached (0.920). This value indicates that the tool has an appropriate stability and satisfies the purposes of this study.
- 5. Steps to build the questionnaire:**
 - Access to the administrative literature and previous studies related to the subject of the study, and to use them in building the questionnaire and drafting its paragraphs.
 - Identify the main areas covered by the questionnaire.
 - The questionnaire is designed in its initial form, reviewed and revised.
 - The questionnaire was presented to (5) arbitrators with experience in academic and statistical fields.
 - In the light of the opinion of the arbitrators, some of the paragraphs of the questionnaire were modified in terms of deletion or addition and modification, so that the questionnaire will be finalized in (25) paragraphs.
- 6. Statistical processing:** After the data was collected, coded and processed using appropriate statistical methods, using SPSS, the researchers used frequency, arithmetical averages, standard deviations and percentages, independent sample T test, mono-variance test, LSD and Cronbach's coefficient alpha equation.

Study Results and Hypothesis Test:

1. Results of the study questions:

The aim of this study is to identify the obstacles facing the application of knowledge management at the Technical University of Palestine (Kadoorei) from the point of view of employees. In order to achieve this, the researchers used a questionnaire consisting of (25) items distributed to a sample of (74) In order to explain the results of the study, the researchers used the following measure:

Table 2: Five - step scale

Degree of approval	SMA		Relative Weight	
	From	To	From	To
Very few	1.00	Less than 1.80	20.00	Less than 36.00
A few	1.80	Less than 2.60	36.00	Less than 52.00
Medium	2.60	Less than 3.40	52.00	Less than 68.00
Large	3.40	Less than 4.20	68.00	Less than 84.00

Very Large	4.20	5.00	84.00	100.00
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1. What are the main obstacles to the application of knowledge management at the Technical University of Palestine (Kadoorei)?
2. Is the level of employee awareness of the obstacles facing the application of knowledge management at the Technical University of Palestine (Kadoorei) different (gender, Work Nature, Education Level, Specialization, years of experience)?

Results:

Question 1: What are the main obstacles to the application of knowledge management at the Technical University of Palestine (Kadoorei)?

This question was answered using the "T" test for one sample, as shown in the following table:

Table 3: Obstacles to the application of knowledge management at the Technical University of Palestine (Kadoorei) in descending order by arithmetic mean

No.	Item	SMA	Standard Deviation	Percentage	Class
1.	Administrative procedures are complex	3.75	1.07	75.0	Large
2.	Lack of specialized courses in knowledge management	3.66	1.10	73.2	Large
3.	Over-centralization	3.66	1.03	73.2	Large
4.	Lack of an independent organizational unit to oversee knowledge management	3.60	1.14	72.0	Large
5.	Resistance to change	3.58	1.03	71.6	Large
6.	Low level of participation of decision making	3.54	1.06	70.8	Large
7.	The University's incentive system	3.53	1.16	70.6	Large
8.	Ignore the thoughts of others	3.52	1.14	70.4	Large
9.	The scarcity of individuals specialized in knowledge management	3.51	1.08	70.2	Large
10.	The existence of negative organizational conflicts	3.47	1.149	69.4	Medium
11.	The prevalence of culture of knowledge monopoly	3.45	1.11	69.0	Medium
12.	Insufficient financial resources to support knowledge management programs	3.43	1.13	68.6	Medium
13.	Do not evoke the future and limit the past and the present	3.43	1.17	68.6	Medium
14.	The scarcity of investment in knowledge management experts to benefit from their experiences	3.42	0.90	68.4	Medium
15.	Weak coordination between the administrative units in the university	3.41	1.07	68.2	Medium
16.	Not to use competition to develop creativity among university staff	3.36	1.02	67.2	Medium
17.	Weak documentation of implicit knowledge	3.33	1.019	66.6	Medium
18.	Lack of a supportive environment for the exchange of knowledge in ideas among all individuals	3.32	1.19	66.4	Medium
19.	Weak access to available knowledge and expertise	3.32	1.04	66.6	Medium
20.	Weak use of available techniques	3.31	1.03	66.2	Medium
21.	Inability to develop information systems and databases	3.21	1.14	64.2	Medium
22.	Not to attract qualified human resources in the field of knowledge management	3.17	1.18	63.4	Medium
23.	Lack of capacity to produce knowledge at the university	3.17	1.22	63.4	Medium
24.	Lack of academic freedom within the university	3.14	1.24	62.8	Medium
25.	Lack of special systems to transfer and share knowledge between employees (Intranet, Internet.)	2.91	1.29	58.2	Few
Total score		3.41	0.62	68.2	Medium

The data in Table (3) shows the following:

- The obstacles to the application of knowledge management at the Technical University of Palestine (Kadoorei) were between the few and the large. The percentages ranged from (58.2) to (75.0). This result indicates that the degree of problems, determinants and obstacles to the application of knowledge management at the Technical University of Palestine (Kadoorei) was medium, in terms of the percentage of (68.2).
- The top of the paragraphs were: (Obstacles to the complex administrative procedures pursued by the university, the scarcity of training courses in this area, the excessive centralization, the university's lack of an independent organizational unit to oversee knowledge management, resistance to change, low level of participation of decision makers, The incentives of the university, and the attempt to ignore the ideas of its employees as well as the scarcity of individuals specialized in knowledge management This demonstrates the weakness of the administrative procedures followed by the university and the low rate of courses given to employees to develop and disseminate knowledge and maintain Guardian, also reduced the degree of participation of workers in decision-making and decisions may be due to centralized decisions, which are issued by the Ministry of Higher Education.
- On the other hand, the least obstacles were the absence of special systems for transferring and sharing knowledge management personnel, the lack of academic freedom, the inability to produce knowledge at the university, and the inability of the university to attract qualified human resources in the field of knowledge

management. This demonstrates the existence of systems for the sharing of knowledge among employees and their openness, in addition to granting employees the freedom to teach their courses, conducting research, selecting textbooks, etc., in addition to the interest of the university in attracting human cadres subject to difficult conditions in order to maintain the efficiency of the teaching process.

- The results of the present study are consistent with Al-Othman (2013), which showed a moderate degree of approval among the sample members on the existence of significant obstacles to the application of the reality of knowledge in the university and the study of Al-Shahrani (2010) The success of knowledge management, including the lack of specialized individuals, ignoring the ideas of others, the weak documentation of implicit knowledge, the lack of work teams, the culture of knowledge monopoly, and the constraints imposed by the college administration and the study (Singh, 2008).

2. The results of the hypotheses of the study:

Results on the gender variable the hypothesis states:

There were no statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the mean responses of the sample of the study towards the constraints of the application of knowledge management at the Technical University of Palestine (Kadoorei) due to gender variable.

In order to examine the validity of the sex-related hypothesis, the T-test for independent samples was used and the results of the following table illustrate:

Table 4: Results of test (t) to indicate the differences by sex variable

Obstacles to the application of knowledge management	Gender	The Number	Average	Deviation	T – Value	Level of Significance *
	Male	42	3.39	0.60		
	Female	32	3.43	0.66		

Note through the data in the previous table that:

- There were no statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) in the responses of the sample of the study towards the obstacles to the application of knowledge management at the Technical University of Palestine (Kadoorei) due to gender variable. The value of the significance level was 0.778. .
- The researchers attribute this finding to the fact that the obstacles to the application of knowledge management at the university are noticed by the workers, regardless of gender, because they do similar work.
- These results were consistent with Al-Othman (2013), which showed no statistically significant differences in the study sample trends due to gender variables and Khubash (2009), which showed no statistically significant relationship between the various factors of

the study and the application of knowledge management within The University of Jordan and its constraints are due to gender variables.

Results related to the variable of Work Nature the hypothesis states:

There were no statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the mean responses of the sample of the study towards the constraints of the application of knowledge management at the Technical University of Palestine (Kadoorei) due to the variable of Work Nature.

In order to examine the validity of the hypothesis related to the functional variable, the T test was used for the independent samples and the results of the following table show that:

Table 5: Results of test (t) to indicate the differences according to the variable level of employment

Obstacles to the application of knowledge management	Work Nature	The Number	Average	Deviation	T – Value	Level of Significance *
	Administrative	46	3.42	0.64		
	Faculty member	28	3.38	0.60		

Note through the data in the previous table that:

- There were no statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) in the responses of the sample of the study towards the constraints of the application of knowledge management at the Technical University of Palestine (Kadoorei) due to the variable nature of work.).
- The researchers attribute this result to the fact that knowledge management is necessary at all levels, disciplines and university fields and is observed by all employees regardless of the nature of their work, as well as for the obstacles noted by the administrative and academic alike.
- The results of this study were consistent with Al-Othman (2013), which showed no statistically significant differences in the study sample due to the variable of Work Nature and Khubash (2009)

Knowledge management within the University of Jordan and its constraints are attributed to the variable of Work Nature.

Results related to the Education Level variable. The hypothesis states:

There were no statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the mean responses of the sample of the study towards the constraints of the application of knowledge management at the Technical University of Palestine (Kadoorei) due to the variable of Education Level.

In order to examine the validity of the hypothesis regarding the Education Level variable, the analysis of the mono-variance was used, and the results of the following tables show that:

Table 6: Results of the analysis of the variance of the single variable of Education Level

Obstacles to the application of knowledge management	Source of Contrast	Total Squares	Degree of Freedom	Average Squares	F – Value	Level of Significance
	Between groups	1.412	3	0.471		
	Within groups	27.333	70	.3900		
	Total	28.745	73			

Note through the data in the previous table that:

- There were no statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) in the responses of the sample of the study towards the constraints of the application of knowledge management at the Technical University of Palestine (Kadoorei) due to the variable of Education Level, the value of the level of significance is (0.314) and this value is Larger than (0.05).
- The researchers attribute this result to the fact that knowledge management is essential for all learners and university employees. As we deal with an educational institution whose basis is to deal with knowledge, everyone notices interest or lack of interest in the development and management of knowledge in this institution regardless of qualifications, whether diploma or doctorate.

- The results of this study are consistent with the study of Al-Othman (2013) which showed that there were no statistically significant differences in the trends of the study sample due to the variable of scientific qualification.

Results related to the specialization variable and states:

There were no statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the mean responses of the sample of the study towards the constraints of the application of knowledge management at the Technical University of Palestine (Kadoorei) due to the variable of Specialization.

In order to examine the validity of the hypotheses related to the specialization variable, the T test was used for independent samples and the results of the following table show that:

Table 7: Results of test (T) to indicate differences according to the variable of Specialization

Obstacles to the application of knowledge management	Specialization	The Number	Average	Deviation	T – Value	Level of Significance *
	Applied Sciences	41	3.23	0.65		
	Human sciences	33	3.63	0.52		

Note through the data in the previous table that:

- There were statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) in the mean responses of

the sample of the study towards the obstacles of the application of knowledge management at the Technical University of Palestine (Kadoorei) due to the

specialization variable where the value of (0.006) is less than the specified value (0.05) These differences are in favor of the level of specialization (human sciences) in terms of the arithmetic average which reached (3.63) while the average level (Applied Sciences) (3.23).

- The researchers attributed this result to the low level of humanities disciplines in the use of technologies and the preservation of information on disciplines of applied science.

Results related to the variable years of experience the hypothesis states:

Table 8: Results of variance of the variable years of experience

Obstacles to the application of knowledge management	Source of Contrast	Total Squares	Degree of Freedom	Average Squares	F – Value	Level of Significance *
	Between groups	1.823	3	0.608		
	Within groups	26.923	70	.3850		
	Total	28.745	73			

Note through the data in the previous table that:

- There were no statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) in the responses of the sample of the study towards the constraints of the application of knowledge management at the Technical University of Palestine (Kadoorei) due to variable years of service.).
- The researchers attribute this finding to the fact that employees' sense of limitations in applying the knowledge effect as well as their knowledge of its benefits are not affected by their different levels of expertise.
- The results of this study are consistent with the results of the Othman (2013) study, which showed no statistically significant differences in the trends of the study sample due to the variable years of experience and the study of Khabash (2009), which showed no statistically significant relationship between the different factors of the study and the application of knowledge management Within the University of Jordan and its constraints are attributed to years of experience.

10. RESULTS

- The percentage of approval of the constraints of the application of knowledge management at the Technical University of Palestine (Kadoorei) varied between the few and the large, and the relative weight of the whole axis was 68.2.
- The shortcomings of the University's complex administrative procedures, the paucity of training courses in this area, the over-centralization, the lack of an independent organizational unit to oversee knowledge management, the resistance to change, the low level of participation of decision makers, the incentive system Which is followed by the university, and the attempt to ignore the ideas of its employees as

There were no statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the mean responses of the sample of the study towards the constraints of the application of knowledge management at the Technical University of Palestine (Kadoorei) due to the variable years of experience.

In order to examine the validity of the hypothesis related to the variable years of experience, the analysis of the mono-variance was used. The results of the following tables illustrate this:

well as the scarcity of individuals specialized in knowledge management) a high approval rate and this indicates the existence of imbalance in administrative procedures and weakness in the development of human cadres and attention to it.

- The following paragraph (lack of special systems for transferring and sharing knowledge management personnel, lack of academic freedom, lack of capacity to produce knowledge at the university, and inability of the university to attract qualified human resources in knowledge management) received a low approval rate. This is evidence of the University's interest in transferring and sharing knowledge among employees and granting them full freedom both according to its specialization, in addition to its interest in recruitment procedures and selection of human cadres.
- There were no statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) in the mean responses of the sample of the study towards the obstacles to the application of knowledge management at the Technical University of Palestine (Kadoorei) due to the variables (gender, nature of work, Education Level, years of service).
- There were statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) in the mean responses of the sample of the study towards the obstacles to the application of knowledge management in the Technical University of Palestine (Kadoorei) due to the variable of specialization and in favor of the level of specialization (human sciences) in terms of the arithmetic average which reached (3.63) while the average level of (applied sciences) was (3.23).

11. RECOMMENDATIONS

In the light of previous findings, the researchers recommend:

- The need to pay attention to the principle of knowledge management in order to raise the status of the university and its academic reputation at home and abroad and improve its services to students and the community and the fact that knowledge management is one of the most prominent features of modern management in academic institutions.
- To develop the process of information investment and exchange in the university.
- To accept change and shift towards knowledge management by encouraging the recruitment of cadres and recruiting cadres specialized in this field and training existing cadres.
- The need for the university to systematically monitor the knowledge and information in the academic field from its available sources because of its importance in the academic process and in the development of university work.
- The University should adopt policies that encourage scientific research and knowledge preservation through the provision of budgets to support scientific research projects and the promotion of creative ideas.
- The need to strengthen the exchange of experiences and knowledge with local, regional and international universities in order to enhance the knowledge and preserve it and provide modern and advanced scientific techniques and use them in administrative and academic work at the university.

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